

State Space Modeling and Small-Signal Stability Analysis of a Multiport Soft Open Point Based on the Triple Active Bridge Converter

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Abstract—Soft open points are power electronics devices that allow improved interconnection of two or more feeders in the distribution networks at normally open points to increase the grid controllability, flexibility, resiliency, efficiency, and capacity of hosting distributed energy resources. Furthermore, soft open point capabilities and safety provisions could be further enhanced by including an isolation stage that uses a multiport converter. This paper presents a state space small-signal model and stability analysis of an isolated multiport soft open point based on two-level inverters and the triple active bridge as a DC-DC isolation stage. First, the operation of the multiport soft open point is presented in detail. Then, the modeling process is depicted for each subsystem, including the average model, the linearization process, and finishing with the state space representation. Moreover, the participation factors method is used to identify the states affecting the eigenvalues tending to instability and a sensitivity analysis shows the impact of the electrical and controller parameters on the system stability. The usefulness of the model derived is proved by the stability analysis presented. The results of the sensitivity analysis show the impact of the triple active bridge controller design and grid inductance on the soft open point stability.

Index Terms—multiport converters, small-signal model, soft open points, stability analysis, state space model, triple active bridge.

I. INTRODUCTION

The proliferation of highly variable distributed energy resources (DER) in distribution networks (DN) increases the level of uncertainty in local electricity generation and demand, giving rise to stability and regulation challenges. Current solutions for these issues are in general slow when compared to the fast dynamics imposed by new DER systems like electric vehicle chargers, solar photovoltaic generators, and other power electronics-based DER. Therefore, new solutions such as the soft open point (SOP) are expected to improve DN's flexibility and controllability. The main goal of SOP is to interconnect two or more distribution feeders providing flexible power flow control, relieving grid congestion, and improving grid infrastructure utilization, DN hosting capacity, and grid response under fault scenarios [1], [2]. Moreover, SOP can integrate energy storage or other DERs that can

be shared among the interconnected feeders, which could maximize the hosting capacity of DN [3].

The most common SOP topology in the literature is based on the back-to-back (B2B) connection of two-level voltage source converters. Moreover, the integration of DER in SOPs requires additional conversion stages which, depending on the application, might need to incorporate galvanic isolation for safety and standards compliance. Furthermore, the B2B topology has been enhanced to multiterminal or multiport topologies with more than two interconnected feeders, which increases the potential impact of SOPs in DN but broadens the galvanic isolation concerns [4]. Since B2B SOP topology cannot cope with galvanic isolation, new topologies that include isolated DC-DC converters could further enhance the SOP capabilities and expand the potential applications. However, few studies have been found in electrically isolated multiport SOP topologies, which is the subject of study in this work. Authors in [5] have used the dual active bridge (DAB) to integrate a battery ES into a 2-port SOP. However, only the battery was isolated from the DC bus shared by the B2B SOP, leaving a partially isolated 3-port SOP. Furthermore, authors in [4] have studied a fully isolated 3-port SOP based on the triple active bridge (TAB). The authors proposed and validated a novel DC voltage regulation strategy for a multilevel implementation of this SOP topology.

Stability assessment of power electronics-based solutions with multiple converters connected in series is challenging. This is the case for SOP and solid-state transformer technologies, in which internal interactions and system stability could be affected by subsystem design, controllers, and operation point [6]. Therefore, the development of models of multistage converters that allow stability assessment is of great relevance.

The authors in [6] investigated the impedance interaction in a two-stage AC-DC-DC converter based on the DAB. Furthermore, the authors presented a small-signal model of the system and proposed two control strategies that integrate a virtual impedance between the DAB and the two-level inverter. By shaping the impedance, the authors demonstrated the enhancement in the stability of the system. Also, authors in [7] have used the Middlebrooks criterion to establish the stability of a three-stage (AC-DC-AC) modular solid-state transformer

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based on the DAB. The small-signal model of the solid-state transformer is derived and used to determine its small-signal stability. Also, the authors validated the impedance interactions among its three stages using software simulations. Similarly, authors in [8] proposed a modified impedance stability criterion for a three-stage three-port single-phase solid-state transformer which was based on the small-signal modeling of the system. Other works have investigated the impact of internal interactions between modules in the stability of modular multilevel converters using extended Middlebrooks criteria for three-port DC-DC converters [9] and a generalized Nyquist criterion for Multi-Input/Multi-Output systems in an AC-DC topology [10]. Also, in [11], the authors presented a more detailed work on the state space model and stability analysis of a single-phase three-stage solid-state transformer that uses a similar isolation stage based on the DAB. The stability analysis included different frequency and time-domain approaches and a real-time simulation validation. However, these works were focused on traditional source-load 2-port systems, and most of the works have dealt with the stability assessment based on impedance criterion.

Regarding SOP modeling, average models are commonly used to define the control strategy. The authors of [12] developed an average model of a 3-port B2B SOP and proposed a control strategy to enhance large signal stability by adding virtual capacitance in the DC link voltage control. Also, in [13], authors derived a model for a 3-port SOP based on the modular multilevel topology and proposed a novel control strategy. The model was used to prove the stability enhancement achieved by the proposed control strategy. Nevertheless, the literature on small-signal modeling and stability of SOP is rather scarce. The authors in [14] presented a small-signal model of a multiport B2B SOP for DNs and the stability of the system was established based on the eigenvalues analysis. Furthermore, the authors showed the influence of grid impedance on stability and how the control parameters could be adjusted following an optimization approach.

The TAB and other isolated multiport (MP) converters can enhance SOP topologies, allowing fully isolated multiport connections and integration of shared DER. However, the literature on SOP topologies based on MP converters has been mainly focused on the use of MP converters as building blocks for 2-port modular topologies rather than implementing multiport SOP solutions [15], [16]. Moreover, the stability analysis of this type of converter has not been studied yet. Therefore, the authors of this paper present a small-signal model for an isolated multiport SOP based on the TAB (MP-SOP from now), which can be used to assess the converter stability.

The main contribution of this work is the derivation of a model of the MP-SOP which could be used to establish the system stability and to select the electrical and control parameters that guarantee the desired stability margins. Another contribution is the stability and sensitivity analysis presented here, where the impact of grid connection elements and TAB controller parameters is demonstrated using the eigenvalue

location analysis. Moreover, the participation factors methodology is used to determine the nature of the eigenvalues closer to instability.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows: Section II presents the MP-SOP topology under study, and describes its operation. Section III depicts the MP-SOP small-signal model derivation. Section IV shows the stability and sensitivity analysis for three case studies. Finally, Section V closes the paper with the main conclusions.

II. SYSTEM DESCRIPTION

This section describes the system under study and the main operation considerations.

The SOP is a power electronics solution that aims to replace or enhance the operation of normally open points in DN. The typical configuration is based on the B2B topology which interconnects two different feeders like a normally open point would do. Furthermore, the SOP can provide grid services that the normally open point cannot. This is thanks to the control capabilities of power electronics used in SOP which enhances the controllability, flexibility, and reliability of DN. Furthermore, isolated MP converters like the TAB can enhance SOP safety, voltage adaptation, and DER integration and sharing among multiple feeders.

Fig. 1(a) shows the enhanced SOP based on the TAB. In this work, two out of the three ports are connected to two different distribution feeders represented by the Thevenin equivalents in the point of common coupling of feeders 1 and 2. Additionally, the third port is connected to a DC bidirectional DER represented by a controlled current source, see Fig. 1(a). The SOP topology uses two two-level inverters connected to the feeders, and the TAB fully isolates the three ports in the SOP.

The control mode of the topology is such that inverters 1 and 2 are controlled in Vdc and PQ control modes, respectively. In both cases, the control is realized in the dq synchronous reference frame as depicted in Fig. 1(b). Furthermore, the isolated DC-DC TAB is in charge of v_{dc2} and v_{dc3} regulation, and its control is realized through a PI controller for each output port as in [17].

III. SOP SMALL-SIGNAL MODEL

In this Section, the small-signal model of the SOP topology under study is derived using the state space approach. The states and inputs are defined for each subsystem and the dynamic state equations are presented. Furthermore, the augmented state and input matrices that include the control states are depicted for the three subsystems. The model of the grid assumes pure sinusoidal voltage and balanced operation of the three-phase system. This allows to model the three-phase system in the equivalent synchronous reference frame state variables. Also, it is assumed that the first harmonic approximation can represent the AC signals in the TAB transformer as in [18]. It is important to note that subscripts 1 and 2 refer to both the distribution feeders connected to the inverters and ports 1 and 2 in the TAB, and subscript 3 refers to port 3 in the TAB.

Fig. 1: (a) Block diagram of a MP-SOP, (b) block diagram of the Vdc control mode, (c) block diagram of the PQ control.

Fig. 2: TAB circuit diagram details.

A. Inverter 1 and L filter

The model of inverter 1 includes the grid and filter impedances. In this case, an "L" filter is considered and the equivalent impedance $Z = Z_g + Z_{inv}$ will be used in the model. (1) summarizes how the equivalent resistance and inductance are considered in the model of both inverters.

$$\begin{aligned} R_i &= R_{g_i} + R_{inv_i} \\ L_i &= L_{g_i} + L_{inv_i} \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where i is the number of the inverter and filter.

First, Kirchhoff's voltage law is applied to feeder 1, leading to (2). Note that, in this subsection, all subscripts 1 refer to feeder 1, inverter 1, or DC link 1.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{di_{1,d}}{dt} &= -\frac{R_1}{L_1}i_{1,d} + \omega_1 i_{1,q} - \frac{m_{1,d}v_{dc1}}{L_1} + \frac{v_{g1,d}}{L_1} \\ \frac{di_{1,q}}{dt} &= -\frac{R_1}{L_1}i_{1,q} - \omega_1 i_{1,d} - \frac{m_{1,q}v_{dc1}}{L_1} + \frac{v_{g1,q}}{L_1} \\ \frac{dv_{dc1}}{dt} &= \frac{m_{1,d}i_{1,d}}{C_1} + \frac{m_{1,q}i_{1,q}}{C_1} - I_{TAB1} \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where $v_{g1,dq}$ and $i_{1,dq}$ are the dq feeder voltages and inverter currents respectively, v_{dc1} is the DC link voltage, $m_{1,dq}$ are the dq average modulation indexes of the inverter, R_1 and L_1

are the resistance and inductance of the equivalent impedance between feeder and inverter, ω is the angular frequency of the grid, and I_{TAB1} the current drawn by the TAB.

Then, the model is linearized around an equilibrium point using the small-signal approximation. The small-signal model is built and the small-signal augmented state and input matrices are presented in (3). The state and input vectors are $\mathbf{x}_1 = [\hat{i}_{1,d}, \hat{i}_{1,q}, \hat{v}_{dc1}, \hat{x}_{v_{dc1}}, \hat{x}_{i_{1,d}}, \hat{x}_{i_{1,q}}]$ and $\mathbf{u}_1 = [\hat{m}_{1,d}, \hat{m}_{1,q}]$ respectively.

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{A}_1 &= \begin{bmatrix} -\frac{R_1}{L_1} & \omega_1 & -\frac{M_{1,d}}{L_1} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -\omega_1 & -\frac{R_1}{L_1} & -\frac{M_{1,q}}{L_1} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ \frac{M_{1,d}}{C_1} & \frac{M_{1,q}}{C_1} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -1 & 0 & -k_{pv} & k_{iv} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \\ \mathbf{B}_1 &= \begin{bmatrix} -\frac{V_{dc1}}{L_1} & 0 \\ 0 & -\frac{V_{dc1}}{L_1} \\ 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

where, $\hat{x}_{v_{dc1}}$, $\hat{x}_{i_{1,d}}$, and $\hat{x}_{i_{1,q}}$ are the control states, V_{dc1} and $M_{1,dq}$ are the steady state values of the DC link voltage and average modulation indexes at the equilibrium point, and k_{pv} and k_{iv} are the proportional and integral gains for the DC link voltage controller.

B. Inverter 2 and L filter

The model of inverter 2 follows the same logic as inverter 1. However, since this inverter operates in PQ control mode, only the dq current states appear. Note that, in this subsection, all subscripts 2 refer to feeder 2 or inverter 2.

(4) shows the average model, and the linearized small-signal augmented state and input matrices are presented in (5). The state and input vectors are $\mathbf{x}_2 = [\hat{i}_{2,d}, \hat{i}_{2,q}, \hat{x}_{i_{2,d}}, \hat{x}_{i_{2,q}}]$ and $\mathbf{u}_2 = [\hat{m}_{2,d}, \hat{m}_{2,q}]$ respectively.

TABLE I
MP-SOP PARAMETERS

Parameter		Value
TAB	DC port voltage: $v_{dc1}, v_{dc2}, v_{dc3}$	400, 400, 350 V
	HFT inductance: L_{t1}, L_{t2}, L_{t3}	36.7, 36.5, 36.8 μ H
	HFT resistance: R_{t1}, R_{t2}, R_{t3}	135, 136, 139 m Ω
	Port capacitance: C_1, C_2, C_3	0.4, 0.4 mF
	TAB Switching frequency: f_{swt}	20 kHz
Grid and inverter	Grid voltage (RMS): v_{gi}	240 V
	Grid frequency: f_{gi}	50 Hz
	AC resistances: R_{gi}, R_{inv_i}	100, 10 m Ω
	AC inductances: L_{gi}, L_{inv_i}	0.1, 1.1 mF
	Inverter switching frequency: f_{sw_i}	10 kHz
Operation point	Active power: P_1, P_2, P_3	4, 2, 2 kW
	Reactive power: Q_1, Q_2	0, 0 kVA

$$\frac{di_{2,d}}{dt} = -\frac{R_2}{L_2}i_{2,d} + \omega_2 i_{2,q} - \frac{m_{2,d}v_{dc2}}{L_2} + \frac{v_{g_{2,d}}}{L_2} \quad (4)$$

$$\frac{di_{2,q}}{dt} = -\frac{R_2}{L_2}i_{2,q} - \omega_2 i_{2,d} - \frac{m_{2,q}v_{dc2}}{L_2} + \frac{v_{g_{2,q}}}{L_2}$$

$$\mathbf{A}_2 = \begin{bmatrix} -\frac{R_2}{L_2} & \omega_2 & 0 & 0 \\ -\omega_2 & -\frac{R_2}{L_2} & 0 & 0 \\ -1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (5)$$

$$\mathbf{B}_2 = \begin{bmatrix} -\frac{V_{dc2}}{L_2} & 0 \\ 0 & -\frac{V_{dc2}}{L_2} \\ 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

where $v_{g_{2,dq}}$ and $i_{2,dq}$ are the dq feeder voltages and inverter currents respectively, V_{dc2} is the steady state DC link voltage in the equilibrium point, R_2 and L_2 are the equivalent resistance and inductance of the equivalent impedance between feeder and inverter, and $\hat{x}_{i_{2,d}}$, and $\hat{x}_{i_{2,q}}$ are the control states.

C. Triple Active Bridge

The full-order TAB average model was derived using the generalized average model approach as in [18]. The linearized model is obtained using the small-signal approximation and the linear small-signal augmented state and input matrices are presented in (6). The state and input vectors are $\mathbf{x}_3 = [\hat{v}_{dc2}, \hat{i}_{2,Re}, \hat{i}_{2,Im}, \hat{v}_{dc3}, \hat{i}_{3,Re}, \hat{i}_{3,Im}, \hat{x}_{v_{dc2}}, \hat{x}_{v_{dc3}}]$ and $\mathbf{u}_3 = [\hat{\varphi}_{1,2}, \hat{\varphi}_{1,3}]$ respectively.

$$\mathbf{A}_3 = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & \frac{4 \sin \varphi_2}{\pi C_2} & \frac{4 \cos \varphi_2}{\pi C_2} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ m_1 & -\frac{R_{t2}}{L_{t2}} & \omega_{swt} & m_2 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ m_3 & -\omega_{swt} & -\frac{R_{t2}}{L_{t2}} & m_4 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{4 \sin \varphi_3}{\pi C_3} & \frac{4 \cos \varphi_3}{\pi C_3} & 0 & 0 \\ m_5 & 0 & 0 & m_6 & -\frac{R_{t3}}{L_{t3}} & \omega_{swt} & 0 & 0 \\ m_7 & 0 & 0 & m_8 & -\omega_{swt} & -\frac{R_{t3}}{L_{t3}} & 0 & 0 \\ -1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & -1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\mathbf{B}_3 = \begin{bmatrix} \beta_1 & 0 \\ \beta_2 & \beta_3 \\ \beta_4 & \beta_5 \\ 0 & \beta_6 \\ \beta_7 & \beta_8 \\ \beta_9 & \beta_{10} \\ 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (6)$$

where $\hat{i}_{2,Re}, \hat{i}_{2,Im}, \hat{i}_{3,Re},$ and $\hat{i}_{3,Im}$ are the real and imaginary components of the first harmonic approximation of the transformer currents in port 2 and 3 of the TAB respectively, $\hat{v}_{dc3}, \hat{x}_{v_{dc2}}, \hat{v}_{dc3},$ and $\hat{x}_{v_{dc3}}$ are the voltages at port 2 and 3 with their respective control states, $R_{t2}, L_{t2}, R_{t3},$ and L_{t3} are the leakage inductance and parasitic resistances of port 2 and 3 in the high-frequency transformer (HFT), ω_{sw} is the switching

TABLE II
EIGENVALUES

Eigenvalue	Value	State
λ_1	-86.57	$\hat{x}_{i_{2,d}}, \hat{x}_{v_{dc2}}$
λ_2	-90.95	$\hat{x}_{i_{1,q}}$
λ_3	-90.95	$\hat{x}_{i_{2,q}}$
λ_4	-91.16	$\hat{x}_{i_{1,d}}$
λ_5	-133.84	$\hat{x}_{v_{dc3}}$
λ_6	-155.70	$\hat{x}_{v_{dc2}}$
λ_7, λ_8	-170.98 \pm 464.20i	$\hat{x}_{v_{dc1}}, \hat{v}_{dc1}$
λ_9, λ_{10}	-1170.40 \pm 125890i	$\hat{i}_{3,Re}, \hat{i}_{3,Im}$
λ_{11}	-1752.40	$\hat{v}_{dc2}, \hat{v}_{dc3}$
$\lambda_{12}, \lambda_{13}$	-2968.20 \pm 125740i	$\hat{i}_{2,Re}, \hat{i}_{2,Im}$
λ_{14}	-5483.10	$\hat{v}_{dc3}, \hat{v}_{dc2}$
λ_{15}	-11839.41	$i_{1,d}$
λ_{16}	-12566.37	$i_{1,q}$
λ_{17}	-12566.37	$i_{2,q}$
λ_{18}	-12692.97	$i_{2,d}$

frequency, and m_{1-8} and β_{1-10} are constants that depend on the operation point if the TAB and the resultant equivalent inductances of the equivalent circuit of the HFT [18].

D. Complete model

Once the subsystem models are developed, they are linked together in an aggregated small-signal model as in (7). The connection matrices \mathbf{T} are used to interconnect the subsystem models. Most of the entries in the connection matrices are zero, and the non-zero entries of the connection matrices are presented in the section VI. The stability analysis presented in this work is based on the small-signal feedback state space model $\mathbf{A}_{fb} = \mathbf{A} - \mathbf{BK}$, with \mathbf{K} being the controller gain matrix. The complete model is not presented here due to space limitations.

$$\mathbf{A} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{A}_1 & \mathbf{T}_1^x & \mathbf{T}_2^x \\ \mathbf{T}_3^x & \mathbf{A}_2 & \mathbf{T}_4^x \\ \mathbf{T}_5^x & \mathbf{T}_6^x & \mathbf{A}_3 \end{bmatrix} \quad (7)$$

$$\mathbf{B} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{B}_1 & \mathbf{T}_1^u & \mathbf{T}_2^u \\ \mathbf{T}_3^u & \mathbf{B}_2 & \mathbf{T}_4^u \\ \mathbf{T}_5^u & \mathbf{T}_6^u & \mathbf{B}_3 \end{bmatrix}$$

Fig. 3: Participation factors for the MP-SOP.

IV. RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

Once the small-signal model of the MP-SOP is derived, it is coded in the MATLAB environment which is used to determine the system stability. Furthermore, the critical eigenvalues and the state's participation at a given equilibrium point are determined using the participation factors method. With that information, a sensitivity analysis is carried out, which contributes to evaluating the effect of certain parameters on the system's stability. The participation factors and sensitivity analysis of eigenvalues of the MP-SOP system are presented and discussed in this Section.

The system parameters and operation point values are presented in Table I. Furthermore, the full-order eigenvalues are presented in Table II, and the participation factors presented in Fig. 3 are used to infer the states that affect each eigenvalue. Moreover, the participation factors and the analysis of the eigenvalues presented in Table II allow for inferring the criticality of the eigenvalues and the parameters that could affect the stability.

The eigenvalue analysis reveals that the fastest eigenvalues λ_{15-18} are the dq currents of both inverters and can be discarded in stability analysis. Furthermore, it shows that eigenvalues closer to instability are fully damped. The sensitivity analysis did not reveal a critical movement in λ_{1-6} that could threaten the system's stability. On the other hand, eigenvalues $\lambda_{7,8}$ show oscillatory behavior and could threaten the system stability as follows. These eigenvalues are influenced by the DC voltage linking the inverter 1 to the TAB, v_{dc1} . At the equilibrium point, these eigenvalues have a damping factor of 34%, which decreases as the value of L_1 increases. Fig. 4 shows the movement of eigenvalues $\lambda_{7,8}$ when L_1 is increased from $0.1L_1$ to $11L_1$. The eigenvalues reach the right-hand plane around $L_1^{critical} = 10L_1$. Moreover, the system's stability could be threatened at $L_1 < L_1^{critical}$. For instance, if C_1 is

Fig. 4: $\lambda_{7,8}$ location when increasing the grid inductance L_1 .

10% lower and L_1 is 6 times greater, this mode's frequency is around 100Hz, and its damping is $<10\%$. It is relevant to highlight that the degraded damping for this oscillation mode could threaten the system stability, especially under an unbalanced operation of the three-phase system which creates oscillations in the DC-link voltage at $2f_{gi}$ that could resonate with this mode [19]. Furthermore, the sensitivity analysis helps identify that decreasing the voltage controller bandwidth or increasing the DC-link capacitance could improve the stability of the system when the equivalent impedance increases, see Fig. 4.

Moreover, the eigenvalues $\lambda_{10,11}$ and $\lambda_{13,14}$ are mostly affected by the AC currents in the HFT, and their damping factor and oscillation frequency are consistent with the switching frequency and AC nature. These oscillation modes associated with the HFT are far from instability and, in principle, they should not threaten the system's stability. However, when the bandwidth of the TAB voltage controller is increased, $\lambda_{10,11}$ starts moving to the right-hand plane as presented in Fig. 5. The controller bandwidth is increased from $0.6BW_{v_{dc2}}$ to $2BW_{v_{dc2}}$ of the equilibrium point. In both figures, the black dots show the location of the eigenvalues at the equilibrium point, and the arrows indicate how the eigenvalues move in the complex plane as the voltage controller bandwidth increases.

V. CONCLUSION

In this work, the derivation process of a state space small signal model of a three-port isolated soft open point was carried out. The model of the three stages was derived separately, including two grid-connected inverters and a triple active bridge. Once the MP-SOP model was obtained, the stability of the system was assessed using the participation factors and a sensitivity analysis. The eigenvalue location was instigated for two cases where the stability of the system could be threatened. The sensitivity analysis showed that the stability of the system is affected by the equivalent impedance connected to the inverters and the bandwidth of the DC voltage controllers. Furthermore, the sensitivity analysis also showed that increasing the capacitance of C_1 to the double or

Fig. 5: Eigenvalue location when increasing the bandwidth of the v_{dc2} controller.

decreasing the bandwidth of the voltage controller of the TAB by 25% could enhance the robustness of the MP-SOP when connected through large inductance to the grid.

Future work will be done to assess the impact of grid synchronization, outer control loops, and the interaction of the MP-SOP to the grid. Also, harmonic state space modeling could be used to analyze the impact of non-sinusoidal grid voltages on the MP-SOP stability. Furthermore, real use cases should be considered to quantify the theoretical advantages of using the TAB in distribution networks. In this sense, electric vehicle charging infrastructure and microgrid interconnection, are two of the use cases that will be considered in the future.

VI. APPENDIX

$$\begin{aligned}
 T_{1(3,2)} &= -\frac{4 \sin \varphi_2}{\pi C_1} & T_{1(3,3)} &= -\frac{4 \cos \varphi_2}{\pi C_1} \\
 T_{1(3,5)} &= -\frac{4 \sin \varphi_3}{\pi C_1} & T_{1(3,6)} &= -\frac{4 \sin \varphi_2}{\pi C_1} \\
 T_{3(2,3)} &= -\frac{2n_2 \text{Im}(Z_{t_2})}{\pi L_{t_2}} & T_{3(3,3)} &= \frac{2n_2 \text{Re}(Z_{t_2})}{\pi L_{t_2}} \\
 T_{3(4,3)} &= -\frac{2n_3 \text{Im}(Z_{t_3})}{\pi L_{t_3}} & T_{3(5,3)} &= \frac{2n_3 \text{Re}(Z_{t_3})}{\pi L_{t_3}} \\
 T_{4(1,1)} &= -\frac{M_{2,d}}{C_2} & T_{4(1,2)} &= -\frac{M_{2,q}}{C_2} \\
 T_{6(1,1)} &= -\frac{M_{2,d}}{L_2} & T_{6(2,1)} &= -\frac{M_{2,q}}{L_2}
 \end{aligned}$$

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